

PHYSICAL FACILITIES DEVELOPMENT PLANNING PRACTICES AND FINANCIAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PRACTICES OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN THE THIRD CONGRESSIONAL DISTRICT OF QUEZON

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the schools' level of physical facilities development practices in terms of prioritization, cost-benefit analyses, and capital plans. Additionally, it assesses their financial management practices along with the problems encountered and actions taken. This employed the descriptive method of quantitative research using the researcher-made checklist questionnaire facilitated among teachers and school heads in the Third Congressional District of Quezon for the school year 2022-2023. Data were analyzed using frequency counts, mean, percentage, and Spearman Rho. Findings reveal that the respondents demonstrate a generally high level of practice in physical facilities development planning, particularly in cost benefit and capital planning, although prioritization appears to be fully practiced. Similarly, respondents exhibit a high level of proficiency in financial resources management, including budget preparation, resource mobilization, and auditing and evaluation. However, no significant relationship was found between physical facilities development planning and financial resources management practices. Insufficient funding for infrastructure emerges as a major challenge in physical facilities planning, while limited budgetary allocation is identified as a key issue in financial resource management where respondents advocate for increased government funding and implement prioritization frameworks aligned with immediate school needs. Furthermore, based on the findings, upskilling programs for school heads in managing facilities and financial resources are developed and recommended for review and implementation based on the research findings.

Keywords: *Physical Facilities Development, Planning Practices, Financial Resources Management Practices*

INTRODUCTION

Prioritizing physical facilities enhancement, strategic development planning, and sound financial management, public elementary schools create environments conducive to student success and holistic development. In education, the public elementary schools are the very foundation of a society's educational framework, laying the ground for future success and societal development. The quality of these institutions significantly impacts the academic achievements and overall well-being of students. To ensure optimal learning environments, a comprehensive approach encompassing physical facilities, development planning practices, and financial resource management is paramount.

Moreover, at the forefront of enhancing public elementary schools is the improvement of physical facilities. Adequate infrastructure, including classrooms, libraries, laboratories, and recreational spaces, is essential for creating conducive learning environments. Renovating existing structures and constructing new facilities must align with modern educational standards and accommodate evolving teaching methodologies. Additionally, attention should be given to facilities' accessibility, safety, and sustainability, ensuring inclusivity and environmental responsibility. Development planning practices play a pivotal role in shaping the trajectory of public elementary schools. Long-term strategic plans, informed by thorough needs assessments and community input, provide a roadmap for growth and improvement. Collaborative efforts involving educators, administrators, parents, and local stakeholders foster consensus-driven decision-making and promote accountability. Moreover, flexibility within development plans allows for adaptation to changing demographics, educational trends, and societal needs.

Similarly, effective financial resource management is fundamental to sustaining and advancing public elementary schools. Allocating budgets equitably and transparently ensures that funds are utilized efficiently to address priority areas, such as teacher salaries, instructional materials, and technology integration. Diversifying revenue streams through grants, partnerships, and fundraising initiatives can supplement public funding and support innovative educational initiatives. Moreover, implementing robust financial oversight mechanisms mitigates the risk of mismanagement and enhances accountability to stakeholders. In practice, integrating these components requires a coordinated approach that prioritizes collaboration, innovation, and continuous improvement. Public-private partnerships offer opportunities for leveraging expertise, resources, and best practices to maximize impact. Engaging with educational experts, policymakers, and industry leaders facilitates the exchange of knowledge and promotes innovation in educational practices and infrastructure development.

On a global scale, Nankervis et al. (2019) delve into general human resource management practices, providing a broad overview of strategies and approaches utilized across physical and financial management across different sectors. Meanwhile, Lairson

et al. (2019) focus on financial resource management, particularly within the context of physical therapy, offering insights into the knowledge and skills necessary for effective financial stewardship, albeit without specifying their study location. Additionally, van Noordwijk (2019) in Ohio advocates for integrated natural resource management as a means to alleviate poverty on a global scale, highlighting the interconnectedness between environmental sustainability and socioeconomic development.

Turning to the Asian context, scholars explore various dimensions of management practices tailored to the region's unique challenges and opportunities. Rasool et al. (2019) investigate the impact of physical and financial resource management practices on sustainable organizational performance in Asia, emphasizing the importance of aligning HR strategies with environmental and social objectives same with Ngoc Su et al. (2021) in Vietnam which contributed to business resilience during the COVID-19 crisis, underscoring the adaptive capacity of organizations in the face of unprecedented challenges. Additionally, Li et al. (2019) delve into green physical infrastructure practices for stormwater control, likely within an Asian context, highlighting innovative approaches to sustainable urban development.

Zooming into the Philippines, localized studies provide valuable insights into management practices within the context of a developing country. Acido & Kilongkilong (2022) investigate resource management practices within a public higher institution, shedding light on the challenges and strategies employed to optimize financial resource utilization and physical management in an educational setting. Dela Cruz & Ortega-Dela Cruz (2021) address facility management issues in public healthcare institutions, offering practical recommendations to enhance the quality and efficiency of healthcare delivery in the Philippines. Furthermore, Tayco (2022) explores human resource management practices and their outcomes in accommodation facilities in the central Philippines, emphasizing the importance of workforce management in the hospitality sector for delivering quality service and ensuring customer satisfaction.

Additionally, since schools' physical structures and facilities are vital for the delivery of quality instruction, the Department of Budget and Management, Education gets P924.7 billion in the proposed 2024 national budget, focused expenditure on subsidies, skill development, and facilities enhancement. Accordant to the Department of Budget and Management (DBM, 2023), the higher provision for subsidies, facilities learning materials, and skill training programs comprise the bulk of the 3.3 percent increase in the budget allocation for the education sector in the FY 2024 National Expenditure Program.

With its importance in the field of education, physical and financial management was also supported by the constitution and other legal basis. Public elementary schools in the Philippines fall under the governance of the Department of Education (DepEd), and their development planning and financial management practices are guided by various legal documents and DepEd Memoranda. At the core of these regulations lies a commitment to uphold the constitutional mandate of providing free and quality education to all Filipino children. The Constitution of the Philippines (1987), specifically Article XIV, Section 5(2)(i), underscores the government's responsibility to prioritize education, necessitating

the provision of adequate facilities for schools. Further elaborating on this mandate, the Local Government Code of 1991 (Republic Act No. 7160) designates municipalities and cities as responsible entities for furnishing school buildings and other necessary facilities for public elementary and secondary schools.

In alignment with these legal frameworks, DepEd has issued several memoranda that guide physical facilities development planning and financial resources management practices within public elementary schools. While there isn't a single DepEd Memorandum encompassing both aspects comprehensively, relevant directives have been issued for each area. For physical facilities development planning, DepEd Order No. 24, series of 2022, known as the Basic Education Development Plan 2030, sets forth the overarching direction and policies for the next decade of basic education, with a specific emphasis on ensuring access to safe and adequate school facilities. On the other hand, financial resources management in public elementary schools is governed by specific DepEd Orders. DepEd Order No. 029, series of 2022, known as the School Board Manual, delineates the composition and functions of the School Board, emphasizing its role in approving the School Improvement Plan (SIP). Additionally, DepEd Order No. 046, series of 2012, outlines guidelines for implementing School-Based Management (SBM), a framework that empowers schools to manage their financial resources autonomously.

Despite these support and advocacy of the organization, there are still challenges that were observed in the field of physical and financial management in DepEd. Ruhyana and Aeni (2018) found that there is lack of classroom facilities in the Philippines which has a significant impact on students' learning outcomes. They found that damage to educational facilities, particularly classrooms, was associated with lower learning outcomes and higher rates of grade repetition. Additionally, during her presentation of the Basic Education Report (BER) 2023, Vice President and Education Secretary Sara Duterte underscored the pressing issue of inadequate school infrastructure, acknowledging the imperative to construct and refurbish facilities to accommodate the educational needs of millions of students across the Philippines (DepEd, 2022). With over 28.4 million students enrolled in both public and private schools nationwide, the scarcity of well-maintained facilities is glaring, as evidenced by only a fraction of school buildings deemed to be in good condition.

In the same context like in the Third Congressional District of Quezon, particularly in Catanauan, Mulanay, General Luna, Macalelon and Pitogo, rapid population growth exacerbates the strain on existing facilities, leading to overcrowded classrooms and insufficient resources per student. Overcrowding is a major challenge for Public Elementary Schools in Quezon. With more students than classrooms, schools are forced to hold double shifts or utilize unconventional learning spaces. This can lead to a less conducive learning environment for students, as they have less space and fewer resources. In addition to overcrowding, many school buildings are old and in need of repair. This can include issues with leaking roofs, damaged electrical wiring, and inadequate sanitation facilities. These problems can create safety hazards and make it difficult for students to learn effectively.

With these, the researcher was interested to investigate the status of physical facilities development planning practices implemented by the school heads and Financial Resources Management in their respective school. To improve the whole educational experience and establish surroundings that are conducive to learning for students, this study attempts to give a thorough grasp of how these two essential factors are managed and coordinated. By examining the existing practices, the researcher tried to identify potential areas for improvement and suggest recommendations for better resource allocation and utilization. The information and findings are utilized to design a comprehensive intervention plan aimed at equipping school heads with the necessary knowledge and skills in both financial management and physical facilities development planning practices.

Research Questions

This study determined and analyzed the relationship between Physical Facilities Development Planning Practices and Financial Resources Management Practices of Public Elementary Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon.

Specifically, it tried to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of physical facilities development planning practices of public elementary schools in terms of:

- 1.1 Prioritization
- 1.2 Cost Benefits Analysis, and
- 1.3 Capital Planning?

2. What is the level of financial resources management practices of the school in terms of:

- 2.1 Budget Preparation
- 2.2 Resource Mobilization; and
- 2.3 Auditing and Evaluation?

3. Is there a significant relationship between the physical facilities development planning practices and financial resources management practices of public elementary schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon?

4. What are the problems encountered by the school head in Physical Facilities and Financial Resources Management?

5. What actions are undertaken by the school heads to address the problems encountered in Physical Facilities and Financial Resource Management?

6. What intervention plan could be offered by the researcher based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research employed the descriptive method of research in quantitative research. This allows for an objective understanding of the complex issue of school management. The descriptive method in quantitative research involves systematically observing and summarizing the characteristics, behaviors, or phenomena of a subject or group using numerical data. It emphasizes objectivity and impartiality in data collection and analysis, relying on surveys, questionnaires, observations, or existing records to gather information. Researchers strive to minimize biases and subjective interpretations to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the descriptive findings, which are presented using tables, charts, graphs, or descriptive statistics. It serves as a valuable approach for exploring topics, providing context, and offering insights into real-world phenomena in various fields such as psychology, sociology, education, and market research.

In this research, the descriptive method was employed to assess and describe the levels of physical facilities development planning practices and financial resources management practices within public elementary schools. Through surveys, questionnaires, the researcher gathered numerical data on various aspects such as prioritization, cost-benefit analysis, capital planning, budget preparation, resource mobilization, and auditing and evaluation. These data are then systematically analyzed using descriptive statistics to provide a comprehensive snapshot of the current practices within the schools. With the objective presentation of the characteristics and behaviors related to physical facilities development planning and financial resources management, the study aims to identify any existing patterns, trends, or areas for improvement. Additionally, descriptive findings serve as a foundation for addressing research questions regarding the relationship between these practices, the encountered problems, actions taken by school heads, and potential intervention plans.

Research Locale

Quezon province is a part of Region IV-A CALABARZON of Luzon Island. Upon its creation in 1591, Quezon Province bore the name Kaliraya or Kalilayan, derived from the word "lilay," which refers to a variety of palm tree abundant in the area. Right after it was renamed Quezon to honor the second president of the country, Manuel L. Quezon, who hailed from the province. The Bondoc Peninsula lies in the southeastern part of Quezon Province in the CALABARZON Region IV-A, southern part of Luzon, Philippines. The Bondoc Peninsula consists of 12 municipalities: Agdangan, Buenavista, Catanauan, General Luna, Macalelon, Mulanay, Padre Burgos, Pitogo, San Andres, San Francisco, San Narciso, and Unisan, all in the 3rd Congressional District of Quezon.

Bondoc Peninsula faces specific challenges regarding school facilities or financial management resources compared to other areas. The peninsula's remoteness or island location might create logistical difficulties in obtaining resources or maintaining facilities.

The region's economic situation could limit the school budget, impacting development and maintenance.

By taking a granular approach and focusing on the five distinct districts of Mulanay II, Catanauan I, General Luna, Macalelon, and Pitogo, the researcher can gain a deeper understanding of their unique challenges. This in-depth knowledge was allowed for the development of targeted solutions specifically tailored to address the local needs and conditions of each district, maximizing their effectiveness.

To assess the level of budgeting, cost control, facility maintenance planning, and space utilization practices employed by school heads within the selected congressional district, and how these practices compare to national best practices. This research identified the areas for improvement and recommend specific training programs to enhance financial resource management and physical facilities planning practices within the district, ultimately aiming to improve student outcomes.

Research Population and Sample

The respondents of the study were the school heads and teachers in the third congressional district. Since the school head works with the school board or administration to create a development plan for the facilities. This plan prioritizes projects based on urgency, budget constraints, and potential funding sources. They provide leadership, planning, and advocacy to ensure the facilities support a positive and effective learning experience for students. Teachers can be strong advocates for facility improvements. They can communicate their needs to school administration, parent-teacher associations (PTAs), and even local school boards. By sharing their experiences

and the impact of current facilities on teaching and learning, they can help build a strong case for investment.

To gain a deeper understanding of the district's needs, the researcher deliberately selected municipalities with the most urgent requirements for physical facilities development. This selection focused on areas with critically overcrowded schools, a lack of accessible healthcare facilities, and limited public transportation options. By concentrating efforts on these municipalities, the researcher aims to ensure equitable access to essential services and promote overall development within the Third Congressional District. The targeted approach allows for the development of a program plan that directly addresses the identified needs of the specific population or issue. The municipalities selected through purposive sampling in the Third Congressional District. By strategically focusing on municipalities with the most pressing educational challenges, the research can achieve a deeper understanding of the specific difficulties faced by school heads in those areas.

The researcher opted for a complete enumeration of 14 school heads and 195 teachers within the selected Third Congressional District of Quezon. With complete enumeration, the researcher has access to data from the entire population. It can lead to more statistically powerful findings and a more robust program plan. Five (5) public elementary schools considering its sizes; small, medium and large must involve in the study. Teachers as a respondents had a total sample of 195, they were chosen using a technique of grouping according to the size (large, medium and small) of the school. Teachers are at the forefront of the learning environment. They can provide valuable insights into what improvements would most benefit student learning and well-being.

For the school heads respondents, since they are the leader and the manager of the School Facilities and Financial Management in their respective stations. They are known to forecast, hands on during the process, observe and monitoring as well as conduct of evaluation and make future plans. With their expertise and strategic planning, they would come out into an efficient Facilities and Financial goals. With all these, the researcher believed that their responses are equally important for the delivery of the Physical Facilities and Financial Resources. With that, the research also comprised of 14 schools selected through systematic random sampling. For the school heads respondents there were 7, full pledge school principal, 7 teacher in charge . The school heads were the respondents for the quantitative part of the study.

Table1. *Presents the Respondents of the Study*

Municipalities/	Nameof School	School Size	No. Of School Head	No.of Teachers
Catanuan I	Catanuan ES	Large	1	31
	M-Peregrino ES	Meduim	1	9
	Milagros a ES	Small	1	7
Mulanay II	Mulanay ES	Large	1	24
	Pinagpalahan ES	Meduim	1	11
	Buenavista ES	Small	1	8
Macalelon	Macalelon ES	Large	1	22
	Olongtao ES	Meduim	1	12
	Vista Hermosa ES	Small	1	7
General Luna	General Luna ES	Large	1	24
	Malaya ES	Meduim	1	11
	Bacong ES	Small	1	8
Pitogo	GangahinES	Meduim	1	12
	Cabulihan ES	Small	1	9
TOTAL			14	195

The table displays the municipalities in the Third Congressional District of Quezon, namely: Catanauan , Mulanay , Macalelon, General Luna, and Pitogo. The researcher selected one (1) large school, one (1) medium school, and one (1) small school per municipality. The total number of respondents was 209 which comprised fourteen (14) school heads and one hundred ninety-five (195) teachers. School Heads serve as the primary decision-makers concerning physical facilities development planning and financial management. The research primarily focused on School Head practices while teachers are not directly involved in decision-making, they can offer valuable insights into the impact of current facilities and financial management practices on the learning environment.

Research Instrument

The checklist questionnaire that was developed by the researcher employed in this study aimed to assess the level of development of physical facilities development planning practices among school heads and teachers. It encompassed aspects such as prioritization, cost-benefit analyses, and capital planning. Additionally, it evaluated financial resources, including budget preparation, resource mobilization, auditing, and

evaluation. Each parameter in the physical facilities management practices will comprise eight to ten (10) self-made statements based on readings and in financial resources management (5) self-made statements.

To ensure the validity of the instrument, the researchers consulted three educational practitioners: two principals and one language critic. Their feedback was sought on the questionnaire items, and careful consideration was given to their suggestions for modification, rephrasing, or deletion.

Furthermore, to ensure the content validity of the instrument, the researcher conducted a pilot test with ten (10) teachers from Macalelon District who are not participants in the main study. The researcher carefully analyzed the responses gathered during the pilot test.

This analysis helped to ensure the validity of the questionnaire, its reliability, and internal consistency, and its effectiveness in capturing the intended data. Based on the findings, the researcher refined the questionnaire before administering it to the main study participants. Likewise, the instrument applied the descriptive scale in the following table to measure the respondents' response.

Point Scale	Descriptive Scale	Description
5	Fully Practiced -(FP)	competency to a fully practiced is equivalent to 76% to 100%
4	Highly Practiced - (HP)	competency to a highly practiced is equivalent to 51% to 75%
3	Moderately Practiced - (MP)	competency to a moderately practiced is equivalent to 26% to 50%
2	Less Practiced - (MIP)	competency to a less practiced is equivalent to 1% to 25%
1	Not Practiced- (NP)	competency to not practiced is equivalent to 0%

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher initiates the research process by seeking formal permission from the Public Schools District Supervisors (PSDS) of the selected districts within the Third Congressional District of Quezon Province. The researcher also sent data gathering permits, secured data sharing agreement and followed research ethical considerations in the gathering of quantitative data.

Also, this process entailed sending official letters or electronic communications that outlined the research objectives and requested their consent. The respondents may opt to participate voluntarily or may withdraw from the actual gathering.

Moreover, upon approval of the request, questionnaires on physical facilities development practices and financial management practices were distributed to the chosen respondents for their assessment and answers. The researcher was also aided with google form to facilitate gathering of data in some scenarios that the researcher cannot reached out the respondent personally. After retrieving the questionnaire, the researcher tabulated, analyzed, solved, and interpreted the data through the statistician, adviser, and other experts in the field.

A program plan would be the end view of this study; hence it will be crafted through formulating goals, objectives, projects/ programs, activities/strategies, budgetary allotment, sources of funds, person/s involved, time frame/ duration, and expected outcomes. Through the use of a program plan, school heads would be equipped with the knowledge, skills, and competence needed for successful Physical Facilities Development implementation and realization.

Ethical Considerations

In the conduct of this study, the researcher firstly secured informed consent that was obtained from all participants, including school administrators, teachers, and other relevant stakeholders, prior to their involvement in the study. Participants were provided with clear information about the purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits of the research, and they were given the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence. Confidentiality and anonymity were also maintained to protect the privacy of participants, ensuring that their responses and personal information were kept secure and not disclosed without their explicit consent. Additionally, the research conducted with integrity, honesty, and transparency, avoiding any form of deception or manipulation. The researchers adhered to ethical guidelines and standards set forth by relevant institutions and regulatory bodies such as the university and DepEd, such as obtaining approval from ethics committees or review boards. Lastly, the findings of the study should be reported accurately and objectively, without bias or distortion, to contribute meaningfully to the body of knowledge and promote the welfare of the participants and the broader

community without harm ensuring that the respondents will be safe and secured all throughout the study.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Data collected were be tallied and presented in a matrix. The variables for the evaluation of Physical Facilities Development Plan and Financial Resources management practices will be computed and analyzed using the following:

First, the researcher applied **frequency count, mean, and SD** to determine the level of development practices of school heads on physical facilities development plans and financial resources management. Also, to identify the potential correlation between the level of development of physical facilities development planning practices and financial resources management, the research employed **Spearman's Rho**. Lastly to analyze the problems encountered and actions undertaken by the school head in Physical Facilities and Financial Resources Management, **frequency count and percentage** were utilized.

RESULTS

Part I. Level of Physical Facilities Development Planning Practices of Public Elementary School in the Third Congressional District of Quezon

Table 2

Level of physical facilities development planning practices of public elementary schools in terms of Prioritization

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1	Mean	SD	VI
1 .Identifies the areas of physical facilities that need to be developed most urgently by consulting the prior data.	91	67	44	0	0	4.23	0.79	FP
2 .Develops and prioritizes a comprehensive school facilities development plan.	97	75	30	0	0	4.33	0.72	FP
3. Prioritizes program anchored on annual plan/ school improvement plan	119	58	25	0	0	4.47	0.71	FP
4. Uses resources efficiently to ensure that schools have the physical facilities	80	77	45	0	0	4.17	0.77	FP

necessary to provide quality education to all learners.								
5.Prioritizes the maintenance and repair of existing physical facilities over new construction projects.	99	65	38	0	0	4.30	0.77	FP
6. Considers the impact of facility improvement projects on student learning and safety when prioritizing resources	69	66	67	0	0	4.01	0.82	FP
7. Collaborates with stakeholders such as students, parents, and staff to prioritize physical facility needs.	52	89	61	0	0	3.96	0.75	HP
8. Communicates effectively the priorities for physical facility improvement to stakeholders.	89	98	15	0	0	4.37	0.62	FP
9. Priorities adequate areas for improvement in a school facilities development plan.	82	63	57	0	0	4.12	0.82	FP
10.Has a system in place for regularly assessing the condition and needs of the school's physical facilities.	137	51	14	0	0	4.61	0.62	FP
Composite Mean						4.26	0.74	FP

Legend: 1.00 – 1.79 *Not Practiced (NP)*
 1.80 – 2.59 *Less Practiced (LP)*
 2.60 – 3.39 *Moderately Practiced (MP)*
 3.40 – 4.19 *Highly Practiced (HP)*
 4.20 – 5.00 *Fully Practiced (FP)*

Table 3

Level of physical facilities development planning practices of public elementary school in terms of Cost Benefits Analysis

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1	MEAN	SD	VI
1. Put into practice the rules, regulations, and policies established by the school for the ongoing improvement of its physical facilities.	78	62	62	0	0	4.08	0.83	HP
2. Conduct the importance of cost-benefit analysis when making decisions about physical facility improvements.	66	48	82	6	0	3.86	0.91	HP
3. Improve adequate financial resources and the overall appearance of school physical facilities.	88	44	64	6	0	4.06	0.93	HP
4. Have an appropriate financial resources management plan to improve the safety of school physical facilities.	66	68	66	2	0	3.98	0.83	HP
5. Have proper financial resources management to support student learning and engagement through physical facilities development.	40	60	94	8	0	3.65	0.84	HP
6. Have the knowledge and skills to conduct a thorough cost-benefit analysis	102	39	60	1	0	4.20	0.89	FP
7. Enable schools to provide modern and efficient physical facilities.	34	115	51	2	0	3.90	0.67	HP
8. Involve stakeholders such as students, parents, and staff in the cost-benefit analysis process.	31	75	92	4	0	3.66	0.76	HP
9. Use data and evidence to inform the cost-benefit analysis process.	90	63	49	0	0	4.20	0.81	FP

10. Have significant investment of financial resources is necessary to replace outdated equipment and infrastructure in school physical facilities.	55	103	44	0	0	4.05	0.70	HP
Composite Mean						3.96	0.82	HP

Legend: 1.00 – 1.79 *Not Practiced (NP)*
1.80 – 2.59 *Less Practiced (LP)*
2.60 – 3.39 *Moderately Practiced (MP)*
3.40 – 4.19 *Highly Practiced (HP)*
4.20 – 5.00 *Fully Practiced (FP)*

Table 4

Level of physical facilities development planning practices of public elementary schools in terms of Capital Planning

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1	MEAN	SD	VI
1. Have a clear understanding of the school's physical facility needs and regularly review and update the capital plan based on changing needs and available financial resources.	20	128	54	0	0	3.83	0.58	HP
2. Have a proper resources management plan to enhance the accessibility and usability of school physical facilities.	89	93	20	0	0	4.34	0.65	FP
3. Have an adequate resource to ensure that school physical facilities are well-maintained and sustainable over time	15	110	77	0	0	3.69	0.60	HP
4. Helps schools to meet regulatory requirements for school physical facilities improvements based on need, and impact on student learning.	9	120	73	0	0	3.68	0.55	HP

5. Implements indispensable improvement outlined in a school facilities development.	88	64	50	0	0	4.19	0.81	HP
6. Enable the schools to meet the regulatory requirements for school physical facilities development.	128	62	12	0	0	4.57	0.60	FP
7. Support the long-term success of a school facilities development plan	37	61	77	27	0	3.53	0.94	HP
8. Create a plan based on the identified problems and intervention.	43	38	103	18	0	3.52	0.93	HP
9. Regularly reviews and updates the capital plan based on changing needs and available financial resources.	112	50	40	0	0	4.36	0.79	FP
10. Have sufficient resources to improve the comfort and convenience of school physical facilities.	68	72	62	0	0	4.03	0.80	HP
Composite Mean						3.98	0.73	HP
Grand Mean						4.07	0.76	HP

Legend: 1.00 – 1.79 *Not Practiced (NP)*
1.80 – 2.59 *Less Practiced (LP)*
2.60 – 3.39 *Moderately Practiced (MP)*
3.40 – 4.19 *Highly Practiced (HP)*
4.20 – 5.00 *Fully Practiced (FP)*

Part II. Level of Financial Resources Management Practices of Public Elementary Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon

Table 5

Level of financial resources management practices of public elementary school in the Third Congressional District of Quezon in terms of Budget Preparation

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1	Mean	SD	VI
1. Identify the time frame to determine the period for which you want to create the budget, such as a fiscal year, a calendar year, or a project timeline.	113	45	36	8	0	4.30	0.90	FP
2. Gather financial data and collect all the financial data relevant to your budget, including income, expenses, debts, and savings.	48	33	83	38	0	3.45	1.05	HP
3. Estimate income to determine the sources of income for the period, including salaries, profits, and investments.	98	45	51	8	0	4.15	0.94	HP
4. Monitor the budget and once have created the budget, it's important to monitor it regularly to ensure you are staying on track and making any necessary adjustments.	38	83	81	0	0	3.79	0.74	HP
5. Involve estimating and allocating resources to various activities, projects, departments, or organizations within an entity.	71	96	25	10	0	4.13	0.81	HP
Composite Mean						3.96	0.89	HP

Legend: 1.00 – 1.79 *Not Practiced (NP)*
 1.80 – 2.59 *Less Practiced (LP)*
 2.60 – 3.39 *Moderately Practiced (MP)*
 3.40 – 4.19 *Highly Practiced (HP)*
 4.20 – 5.00 *Fully Practiced (FP)*

Table 6

Level of financial resources management practices of public elementary school in the Third Congressional District of Quezon in terms of Resource Mobilization

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1	MEAN	SD	VI
1. Have clear understanding of the organization's goals, a strong network of partners and supporters, effective communication and marketing strategies, and sound financial management practices.	38	91	61	12	0	3.77	0.82	HP
2. Require continuous adaptation and innovation to ensure that resources are used efficiently and effectively to achieve the desired outcomes.	86	52	64	0	0	4.11	0.86	HP
3. Identify, secures, and manages resources to support programs and initiatives that improve the lives of people and communities	43	69	90	0	0	3.77	0.78	HP
4. Enable organizations to leverage their resources to achieve their goals more effectively.	31	103	68	0	0	3.82	0.68	HP
5. Present report in a timely manner in agreement with the format agreed to with the sponsor	87	65	47	3	0	4.17	0.84	HP
Composite Mean						3.93	0.79	HP

Legend:

- 1.00 – 1.79 *Not Practiced (NP)*
- 1.80 – 2.59 *Less Practiced (LP)*
- 2.60 – 3.39 *Moderately Practiced (MP)*
- 3.40 – 4.19 *Highly Practiced (HP)*
- 4.20 – 5.00 *Fully Practiced (FP)*

Table 7

Level of financial resources management practices of public elementary schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon in terms of Auditing and Evaluation

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1	MEAN	SD	VI
1. Examine and reviewing financial records, transactions, and other relevant documents to ensure that they are accurate, complete, and in compliance with relevant laws and regulations and post in the transparency board.	4	11 1	8 4	3	0	3.57	0.56	HP
2. Provide an independent assessment of the financial health and performance of an organization, and to identify any potential risks or areas for improvement.	11 1	57	2 3	1 1	0	4.33	0.88	FP
3. Collect and analyzes data to determine whether the initiative has achieved its intended outcomes and objectives	26	83	8 5	8	0	3.63	0.76	HP
4. Focus on assessing the performance and effectiveness of an organization or initiative	0	10 7	9 5		0	3.53	0.50	HP
5. Create a consolidated budget report or financial statement.	65	74	5 3	1 0	0	3.96	0.89	HP
Composite Mean						3.80	0.72	HP
Grand Mean						3.90	0.80	HP

Legend:

- 1.00 – 1.79 *Not Practiced (NP)*
- 1.80 – 2.59 *Less Practiced (LP)*
- 2.60 – 3.39 *Moderately Practiced (MP)*
- 3.40 – 4.19 *Highly Practiced (HP)*
- 4.20 – 5.00 *Fully Practiced (FP)*

Part III. Significant Relationship Between Physical Facilities Planning Practices and Financial Resources Management Practices of Public Elementary Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon.

Table 8

Significant relationship between the physical facilities development planning practices and financial resources management practices of public elementary schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon

Correlations					Interpretation	Decision
			Mean1	Mean2		
Spearman's rho	Physical Facilities Development Planning Practices (Mean1)	Correlation Coefficient p-value	1.000 .	.010 .885	Not significant	Ho not rejected
	N		202	202		
	Financial Resources Management Practices (Mean2)	Correlation Coefficient p-value	.010 .885	1.000 .		
	N		202	202		

Part IV. Problems Encountered by the School Heads in Physical Facilities and Financial Resources Management in the Third Congressional District of Quezon.

Table 9

Problems Encountered by the School Head in Physical Facilities and Financial Resource Management

Problems Physical Facilities	5	4	3	2	1	Mean	VD
1. Insufficient funding for infrastructure development	9	2	3	0	0	4.43	AE
2. Deteriorating infrastructure/ Facilities	7	3	2	2	0	4.07	OE
3. Lack of expertise of School Head about facility planning	2	5	5	2	0	3.50	OE
4. Shortage of classroom	8	4	1	1	0	4.36	OE
5. Limited Access to Basic Amenities	5	5	2	2	0	3.93	OE
6. Community Expectations and Pressure	4	4	5	1	0	3.79	OE
7. Inspections of school buildings and grounds	6	2	5	1	0	3.93	OE
8. Students and teachers can become distracted by facilities issue. (HVAC)	0	7	5	2	0	3.36	OE
Problems Financial Resources Management							
1. Limited Budgetary Allocation	10	3	1	0	0	4.64	AE

2. Complex Budgeting Processes	8	4	2	0	0	4.43	OE
3. Financial Reporting and Accountability	3	7	2	2	0	3.79	OE
4. Competing Priorities and Resource Allocation Challenges	3	7	4	0	0	3.93	OE
5. Revenue Generation and Fundraising	6	5	2	1	0	4.14	OE
6. Financial Sustainability Planning	5	5	3	1	0	4.00	OE
7. Budgeting and Expenditure Tracking Practices	7	3	4	0	0	4.21	OE
8. Lack of Transparency and Accountability in Financial Management	2	6	3	2	1	3.43	SE

Legend: “Never Encountered (1.00 – 1.50)”,
“Rarely Encountered (1.51 – 2.50)”,
“Sometimes Encountered (2.51 – 3.50)”,
“Often Encountered (3.51 – 4.50)”,
“Always Encountered (4.51 – 5.00)”

Part V. Actions Taken by the School Heads to Address Problems in Physical Facilities and Financial Resources Management

Table 10

Actions Taken by the School Heads to Address Problems in Physical Facilities and Financial Resources Management in the Third Congressional District of Quezon.

Problems in Physical Facilities	Action/s Taken	f	%	Rank
1. Public schools often receive insufficient	1. Increased government funding and resource allocation for school infrastructure development.	10	71.43	1

funding for infrastructure development, leading to delays or limitations in implementing plans.	2. Redirected underutilized school MOOE funds	1	7.14	5
	3. Utilized Special Education Fund (SEF) in coordination with the LGUs	6	42.86	3.5
	4. Leveraging the Adopt-a-School Program to cultivate deeper engagement and mutual support with diverse development partners, including both internal and external stakeholders	7	50.00	2
	5. Optimizing Brigada Eskwela for increased private sector engagement, leading to maximized resource mobilization for school preparation.	6	42.86	3.5
	Others (Please specify)			
2.Schools have outdated or deteriorating infrastructure, requiring extensive repairs or reconstruction	1. Recalibrated available local funds through alignment and modification of school PPAs	10	71.43	1
	2. Re-allotted available School MOOE Fund	9	64.29	2
	3. Utilized Special Education Fund (SEF) in coordination with the LGUs	5	35.71	4
	4. Enhanced partnerships with Development partners (internal and external stakeholders) through Adopt-a-School Program (ASP)	8	57.14	3
	5. Enhanced Brigada Eskwela and maximized private sectors contribution	4	28.57	5
	Others (Please specify)			
3.Lack of expertise, School heads may not have the necessary background or training in facility planning and	1. Held strengths and needs assessment for school head	7	50.00	1.5
	2. Conducted School-based LAC Sessions and INSETs	6	42.86	3
	3. Attended different DepEd initiated online/virtual trainings and webinars	7	50.00	1.5

project management.	4. Participated in different trainings and webinars sponsored by NEAP Accredited organizations	3	21.43	6
	5. Allocated MOOE Fund for the conduct of school INSET and LAC sessions	3	35.17	4.5
	6. Maximized partnership with internal and external stakeholders in appropriating funds for the conduct of school INSET and LAC sessions through ASP	3	35.17	4.5
	Others (Please specify)			
4.Shortage of classroom	1. Implements various construction programs, including: Building new classrooms, Repairing existing damaged or dilapidated structures, Utilizing public-private partnerships to accelerate construction by the DepEd	14	100	1
	2. Enhanced Brigada Eskwela and maximized private sectors contribution	4	28.57	3
	3. Enhanced partnerships with Development partners (internal and external stakeholders) through Adopt-a-School Program (ASP)	6	42.86	2
5.Limited Access to Basic Amenities	1. Intensified NGOs often work in partnership with communities to provide basic amenities like clean water, sanitation facilities, and healthcare services. They may also offer training and resources to empower communities to manage their own resources.	10	71.43	1
	2. Increased local communities organization and participation in projects to improve their access to basic amenities. .	3	21.43	3.5
	3. Explored new technologies like solar panels, microgrids, and rainwater harvesting systems are making it possible to provide basic amenities in	6	42.86	2

	areas with limited access to traditional infrastructure.			
	4. Utilized mobile apps and platforms can be used to connect communities to information about available resources, healthcare services, and government programs.	3	21.43	3.5
6.Community Expectations and Pressure	1. Create opportunities for community members to actively participate in decision-making processes and project implementation.	10	71.43	1
	2. Collaborates with NGOs, local businesses, and other stakeholders to leverage resources and expertise.	6	42.86	2
	3. Regularly gather feedback from community members to understand their specific needs and priorities.	5	35.71	3.5
	4. Communicate the long-term vision for the community and how current actions contribute to achieving those goals.	5	35.71	3.5
7.Inspections of school buildings and grounds	1. Conducted routine inspections at defined intervals (e.g., monthly, annually) to identify potential problems early.	9	64.29	2
	2. Addressed minor issues promptly to prevent them from escalating into major problems.	11	78.57	1
	3. Trained school staff and students on safety procedures, hazard identification, and reporting protocols.	4	28.57	3.5
	4. Respond to any safety hazards identified during inspections with urgency and transparency.	4	28.57	3.5

8. Students and teachers can become distracted by facilities issue. (HVAC)	1. Schedule regular inspections and preventative maintenance of the HVAC system to identify and address potential problems before they escalate.	9	64.29	1.5
	2. Informed students and teachers about the importance of maintaining a healthy learning environment and the impact of HVAC issues on their well-being.	9	64.29	1.5
	3. Encourage reporting any discomfort or malfunctioning equipment promptly	7	50.00	3
Problems in Financial Resource Management	Action/s Taken	f	%	Rank
1. Limited Budgetary Allocation	1. Conducted a thorough assessment of the school's most pressing needs, considering infrastructure repairs, equipment upgrades, learning materials, and staff development.	10	71.43	2
	2. Developed a clear prioritization framework based on the needs assessment, focusing on critical areas that directly impact student learning and safety.	11	78.57	1
	3. Explored cost-effective solutions for addressing identified needs. This might involve seeking used equipment, negotiating bulk discounts, or considering alternative materials.	4	28.57	5
	4. Tracked and monitored budget utilization to ensure efficient spending and identify areas where adjustments might be necessary.	7	50.00	3.5

	5. Allocated available funds strategically, focusing on the most critical needs identified in the prioritization framework.	7	50.00	3.5
2. Complex Budgeting Processes	1. Implement standardized budgeting templates, guidelines, and reporting formats across all departments.	5	35.71	3.5
	2. Identified and eliminated unnecessary steps or approvals within the budgeting process.	8	57.14	1.5
	3. Established clear communication channels between school administration, department heads, and those involved in the budgeting process.	8	57.14	1.5
	4. Organized training workshops for school staff involved in budgeting, equipping them with the necessary skills and knowledge.	5	35.71	3.5
3. Financial Reporting and Accountability	1. Established a clear and comprehensive financial management policy outlining procedures for budgeting, spending, record-keeping, and internal controls.	8	57.14	2
	2. Implemented a system where different individuals handle different aspects of financial management, such as authorization, recording, and reconciliation.	10	71.43	1
	3. Utilize standardized financial reporting formats that are clear, concise, and easy to understand for stakeholders.	1	7.14	4
	4. Seek guidance and support from financial professionals or external auditors to ensure compliance with regulations and best practices.	5	35.71	3

4. Competing Priorities and Resource Allocation Challenges	1. Establish a clear vision and mission for the school that outlines its core values and long-term goals.	7	50.00	2
	2. Create a transparent prioritization framework based on the needs assessment, focusing on objectives that directly contribute to the school's vision and student learning outcomes.	10	71.43	1
	3. Clearly communicate the rationale behind resource allocation decisions, explaining the needs being addressed and the expected outcomes.	3	21.43	3.5
	4. Evaluate the potential benefits and costs of different resource allocation options before making decisions.	3	21.43	3.5
5. Revenue Generation and Fundraising	1. Conducted a thorough assessment of the school's needs and funding gaps, identifying areas where additional resources are crucial.	11	78.57	1
	2. Established specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound fundraising goals aligned with identified needs.	8	57.14	2
	3. Explored various fundraising avenues beyond traditional methods, such as grants, corporate sponsorships, alumni donations, and social enterprises.	2	14.29	4
	4. Encouraged students and families to participate in peer-to-peer fundraising campaigns through online platforms or sponsored activities.	6	42.86	3
	1. Forecast future income streams and expenses based on enrollment trends,	10	71.43	1

6. Financial Sustainability Planning	economic conditions, and potential changes in government funding.			
	2. Explored various income sources beyond traditional government funding, such as fundraising initiatives, grants, partnerships with businesses, or social enterprises.	9	64.29	2
	3. Identified areas where operational costs can be reduced or streamlined without compromising the quality of education.	4	28.57	4
	4. Published clear and accessible financial reports for stakeholders, including the school community and government agencies.	6	42.86	3
7. Budgeting and Expenditure Tracking Practices	1. Established a standardized budgeting framework with defined categories, timelines, and approval procedures.	9	64.29	1.5
	2. Allocated resources based on identified needs and priorities, focusing on areas directly impacting student learning and achievement.	9	64.29	1.5
	3. Implemented budgeting and expenditure tracking software to automate data entry, generate reports, and facilitate real-time monitoring.	4	28.57	3.5
	4. Analyze variances between planned and actual expenditures to identify areas for improvement or cost-saving opportunities.	4	28.57	3.5
8. Lack of Transparency	1. Organized open meetings or forums where school administration discusses	8	57.14	1.5

and Accountability in Financial Management	financial matters and addresses questions from stakeholders.			
	2. Conduct regular internal audits by qualified personnel to identify any irregularities or discrepancies in financial records.	7	50.00	3
	3. Provide training for school staff on financial transparency, accountability practices, and best practices in financial management.	8	57.14	1.5
	4. Encourage the school community to participate in discussions about financial matters and hold the administration accountable.	3	21.43	4

Table 11

Proposed Intervention Plan

Dimensions	Indicators	Areas for Improvement Based on Findings	Proposed Action
Level of Physical Facilities Development Practices	Prioritization	Collaboration with stakeholders such as students, parents, and staff to prioritize physical facility needs.	Establish regular meetings or forums involving stakeholders to assess and prioritize physical facility needs based on importance and urgency.
	Cost Benefit Analysis	Proper financial resources management to support student learning and engagement through physical facilities development.	Conduct cost-benefit analyses for proposed physical facility projects to ensure efficient allocation of financial resources and maximize benefits for students.

	Capital Planning	Creation of a plan based on the identified problems and intervention.	Develop a comprehensive capital plan outlining short-term and long-term goals for addressing identified physical facility issues, incorporating input from stakeholders.
Level of Financial Resources Management Practices	Budget Preparation	Gathering and collecting all the financial data relevant to budget, including income, expenses, debts, and savings.	Implement a standardized process for gathering and organizing financial data to facilitate accurate budget preparation and decision-making.
	Resource Mobilization	Clear understanding of the organization's goals, a strong network of partners and supporters, effective communication and marketing strategies, and sound financial management sources and practices.	Strengthen partnerships with stakeholders, streamline communication channels, and enhance financial management practices to optimize resource mobilization efforts.
	Auditing and Evaluation	Focus on assessing the performance and effectiveness of an organization or initiative	Implement regular auditing and evaluation procedures to assess the financial health and performance of the organization, identify areas for improvement, and ensure accountability.
Problems Encountered	Physical Facilities	Insufficient funding for infrastructure development	Advocate for increased government funding, explore alternative funding sources, and prioritize infrastructure projects based on critical needs and available resources.

	Financial Resource Management	Limited Budgetary Allocation	Develop a comprehensive budget prioritization framework based on needs assessment, streamline budget processes, and explore cost-saving measures to maximize budget allocation.
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DISCUSSION

Part I. Level of Physical Facilities Development Planning Practices of Public Elementary School in the Third Congressional District of Quezon

The table 2 depicts the level of physical facilities development planning practices of public elementary schools in terms of prioritization. Finding revealed that the prioritization practices in physical facilities management was fully practiced with the composite mean of 4.26. Likewise, this primarily concern the respondents having a system in place for regularly assessing the condition and needs of the school's physical facilities (4.61), prioritizing program anchored on annual plan / school improvement plan (4.47), and communicating effectively the priorities for physical facility improvement to stakeholders (4.37) which are all described as fully practiced. The fully practiced level in prioritization can be traced back from regular supervision of the school head and the supervisors with the collaboration of MDRR coordinators on the hazards and safely and friendly school campaigns of DepEd with regular memoranda from the higher authority. Meanwhile, collaboration with stakeholders earned the lowest mean (3.96) and the highest standard deviation (0.75), indicating variations in practices and potentially less frequent collaboration with the stakeholders and the school.

Findings imply that prioritization in physical facilities development planning practices in public elementary schools are important and given full attention for stakeholders involved in school management and administration. The high level of prioritization practices indicates a proactive approach to assessing and addressing the needs of the school's physical facilities, which can contribute to creating a conducive learning environment for students. However, the lower mean and higher standard deviation for collaboration with stakeholders suggest potential areas for improvement, highlighting the importance of enhancing communication and collaboration among school administrators, teachers, parents, and other relevant stakeholders. Strengthening collaboration can foster shared ownership and responsibility for improvements.

Same with the findings of the study, Chong et al., (2019) also found prioritization as fully practice in certain context because of maintenance in the school that has to be prioritized for learners, teachers, and stakeholders conducive and safe learning environment. Also,

Meyer et al., (2020) found community and stakeholders should be involved in prioritization activities.

Table 3 depicts the level of physical facilities development planning practices of public elementary schools in terms of Cost Benefits Analysis (CBA). The findings reveal a highly practiced level of CBA practices, indicated by a composite mean of 3.96 interpreted as Highly Practiced. Notably, respondents demonstrate having knowledge and skills to conduct a thorough cost-benefit analysis and (4.20) and using of data and evidences to inform the cost-benefit analysis process which are all interpreted as fully practiced. This occurred because of the proper guidelines in management of resources from the central office. On the other hand, all other indicators were down to highly practiced suggesting the need and room for improvement in cost benefit analysis practices. Meanwhile, with the lowest mean of 3.65 and interpreted as highly practiced, having a proper financial resources management to support student learning and engagement through physical facilities development has to be prioritized for improvement. This can be traced back from having insufficient support from DepEd and other stakeholders to lessen the cost of physical improvements in the schools.

The results indicate that public elementary schools exhibit a highly practiced level of CBA practices, indicating a strong foundation in financial resource management. Findings suggest that respondents demonstrate proficiency in conducting thorough cost-benefit analyses and utilizing data and evidence to inform decision-making processes. These competencies are attributed to proper guidelines from the central office, highlighting the importance of centralized support in enhancing CBA practices. However, while certain aspects of CBA are fully practiced, such as knowledge and skills in analysis, there is room for improvement in other areas, particularly in involving stakeholders and ensuring proper financial resource management to support student learning and engagement through physical facilities development. This underscores the need for increased support from DepEd and other stakeholders to address the challenges and enhance CBA practices in public elementary schools, ultimately ensuring the efficient allocation of resources for the benefit of student education and well-being.

Generally, the data suggests that school heads acknowledge the importance of cost-benefit analysis in decision-making for physical facilities. However, there were areas for improvement, particularly in ensuring cost-benefit analysis is directly linked to student learning and that stakeholders are more involved in the process.

Similar with the present findings, Fadahunsi et al. (2019) discovered that cost benefits were maximized through proactive maintenance, improved health and safety standards, a conducive environment, enhanced service quality, and functional buildings. Furthermore, the research identified a range of facility management tools that were implemented at the university, including asset tracking and registers, estate operational plans, cost-benefit analyses, energy use auditing, and control measures. The results of this study highlight the criticality of incorporating comprehensive physical facilities management practices into institutions of higher education in order to maximize the use of resources and improve the overall performance of the organization in a wider scope.

The findings were also aligned with DepEd Order no 36, the Administrators can establish the best learning environment, promote educational goals, adhere to safety regulations, include stakeholders, and maximize the value of the school's physical assets by efficiently planning, maintaining, and enhancing facilities. In the Philippines, the Department of Education has set standards for performing cost-benefit assessments (CBAs) of suggested school projects. DepEd Order No. 36, s., contains a description of the rules.

Table 4 shows the level of physical facilities development planning practices of public elementary schools in terms of Capital Planning. The findings indicate a highly practiced level of Capital Planning practices, with a composite mean of 3.98, interpreted as Highly Practiced. Likewise, the respondents demonstrate proficiency in various aspects of Capital Planning, enabling the schools to meet the regulatory requirements for school physical facilities development (4.57), regularly reviewing and updating the capital plan based on changing needs and available financial resources (4.36), and having proper resources management plan to enhance the accessibility and usability of school physical facilities (4.34) all interpreted as highly practiced. This occurred because of proper school head and supervisor monitoring with monthly regular liquidation and reports from schools concerning the capital plans and the school attainment for the month. However, all other indicators earned the mean lower than 4.20 showing room for improvement as highly practiced particularly in creating a plan based on the identified problems and intervention with the lowest mean of 3.52 interpreted as highly practiced. This can be traced from numerous ancillary works and related task to the personnel in charge of capital planning that management become very overwhelming and identifying needs from data-driven documents were mostly not undertaken.

The identified findings suggest a proactive approach in ensuring that school physical facilities that meet regulatory requirements are regularly updated based on changing needs, and have proper resource management plans for enhanced accessibility and usability. These practices are also deemed crucial for creating a conducive learning environment for students and maintaining the long-term sustainability of school facilities. However, the lower mean scores for certain indicators, particularly in creating plans based on identified problems and interventions, highlight areas for improvement. Strengthening these aspects of Capital Planning, such as streamlining ancillary tasks and ensuring data-driven decision-making, can further enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of resource allocation and management in public elementary schools, ultimately benefiting student education and well-being.

In line with the present findings, relates studies also showed that capital planning is important in meticulously organizing physical facilities development plan is essential for providing functional, safe, and hospitable environments across diverse settings, including urban areas and academic institutions (Morton & Turner, 2021). This can be done with effective planning where Khan and Khan (2019) emphasize the importance of capital assets in indicating an organization's economic health, with well-maintained assets providing crucial support.

Table 5 illustrates the level of financial resources management practices of public elementary schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon, specifically focusing on Budget Preparation. The findings indicate a highly practiced level of Budget Preparation practices, with a composite mean of 3.96, interpreted as Highly Practiced. Also, respondents showed that in budget preparation, the schools primarily identify the time frame to determine the period for which to create the budget such as fiscal year, a calendar year, and a project time with the highest mean of 4.30 and interpreted as fully practiced. This can be due to the school calendar and regular guidelines coupled with memorandum provide by DepEd in concerning school finances and MOOE distribution and liquidation.

Meanwhile, results also showed a proficiency in key aspects of budget preparation, such as estimating income sources (4.15) and monitoring the budget (3.79) show potential for improvement, suggesting the need for more robust data collection processes and consistent monitoring mechanisms. Moreover, findings also showed that with the lowest mean of 3.45, gathering financial data and collecting all the financial data relevant to budge, including income, expenses, and debts, and savings which interpreted as highly practiced need thorough attention for improvement. This happened because of the complexity of liquidation and securing receipts, MOVs, and related documents within the limited time frame.

The findings imply and underscore the significance of effective financial resources management practices in public elementary schools within the Third Congressional District of Quezon. The highly practiced level of Budget Preparation suggests that schools prioritize the establishment of clear time frames for budget creation, reflecting adherence to fiscal year, calendar year, and project timelines. However, despite overall strong performance in budget preparation, areas for improvement exist, particularly in the gathering of financial data, as indicated the need for enhanced data collection processes to ensure comprehensive financial assessments and informed decision-making. Additionally, while estimating income sources and monitoring budgets demonstrate proficiency, opportunities for refining these practices to enhance accuracy and accountability should be explored.

Similar to the identified findings, Klock and Justis (2019) underlined that the need for a school head with operational knowledge in budget preparation with the allotted time frame. Also, Villareal (2023) added that in budget preparation, fund generating supplements planning and revealed the importance of targeted interventions, training programs, and strategic improvements to enhance the budget preparation of the school.

Table 6 presents the level of financial resources management practices of public elementary schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon, focusing on Resource Mobilization. Based on the findings, data revealed a highly practiced level of Resource Mobilization practices, with a composite mean of 3.93, interpreted as highly practiced. Moreover, respondents showed timely presentation of reports in accordance with sponsor-agreed formats (4.17) all interpreted as highly practiced. This can be traced back from division and district consolidation activities of finances and resources of the school

along with the monthly report of adapt a school program in DepEd from every school. Additionally, the respondents also highly practiced requiring continuous adaptation and innovation to ensure that resources are used efficiently (4.11), and enabling organizations to leverage their resources to achieve their goals effectively (3.82). On the other hand, while overall performance in Resource Mobilization is strong, areas for improvement exist, particularly in the clear understanding of organizational goals and sound financial management practices (3.77) and identifying, securing, and managing resources to support programs and initiative that improve the lives of the people and communities (3.77) interpreted as highly practiced. This happened because of the lack of resources and lack of full support from the stakeholders and community leaders on the goals of the school and current financial or resource status.

The results indicate a commendable performance of public elementary schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon in terms of Resource Mobilization. The highly practiced level of Resource Mobilization practices underscores the schools' proficiency in adapting and innovating to ensure efficient resource utilization, as well as in presenting reports in a timely manner as per sponsor-agreed formats. Meanwhile, despite these strengths, areas for improvement are identified, particularly in gaining a clear understanding of organizational goals and enhancing sound financial management practices, as well as in identifying, securing, and managing resources to support programs and initiatives aimed at community improvement. These challenges stem from resource constraints and a lack of full support from stakeholders and community leaders, indicating the need for enhanced collaboration and strategic alignment to optimize resource mobilization efforts and effectively meet organizational objectives.

Additionally, the data suggests that school heads understand some key aspects of resource mobilization, particularly the importance of reporting and efficient resource use. Nevertheless, there were areas for improvement in developing a strong foundation for resource mobilization, such as building a clear understanding of organizational goals, fostering strong partnerships, and ensuring sound financial management practices are in place that will maximize resource mobilization.

Conferring with the current findings, Abdi (2019) also emphasizes the importance of resource mobilization in enabling schools to acquire the necessary materials for providing quality education. This aligns with the findings of Roxas (2019), which highlight government initiatives and collaborative efforts with the private sector as key predictors of resource mobilization. Furthermore, Ralleta (2012) underscores the necessity for schools to continuously seek improvement and adopt innovative approaches to achieve excellence in education. This suggests that resource mobilization efforts should not only focus on acquiring materials but also on fostering a culture of collaboration and innovation within schools. Overall, these studies emphasize the importance of resource mobilization in education and highlight various strategies and initiatives aimed at enhancing educational quality and outcomes.

Table 7 provides insights into the level of financial resources management practices of public elementary schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon, focusing on Auditing and Evaluation. The findings indicate a highly practiced level of Auditing and

Evaluation practices, with a composite mean of 3.80, interpreted as highly practiced. Findings also showed in Auditing and Evaluation, the respondents primarily provide an independent assessment of financial health and performance of the school and to identify potential risks or areas for improvements (4.33) interpreted as fully practiced. This can be traced from regular AIP and SIP planning of finances of the school and in SLAC sessions of the teachers conducted every month. All other indicators were highly practiced such as examining and reviewing financial records, transactions, and other documents (3.57); collecting and analyzing data (3.63), and creating a consolidated budget report or financial statement (3.96) which are all interpreted as highly practiced. Further, while overall performance in Auditing and Evaluation is strong, areas for improvement exist, particularly in focusing on assessing the performance and effectiveness of the organization or initiative (3.53), both interpreted as highly practiced. Additionally, the grand mean considering all data sets is 3.9, indicating a general agreement on the importance of the practices listed across all categories. However, the standard deviation (0.80) suggests some variation in how these practices are implemented.

The findings suggest that public elementary schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon exhibit a highly practiced level of Auditing and Evaluation practices, indicating a commitment to transparency, accountability, and financial health. Also, the comprehensive assessment of financial health and performance demonstrates a systematic approach to identifying potential risks and areas for improvement, facilitated by regular planning sessions and teacher meetings. While the majority of indicators are highly practiced, there are opportunities for further improvement, particularly in assessing the performance and effectiveness of the organization or initiative.

Similar to the current findings, Hall (2019) also underscores the important role of auditing in ensuring the accuracy and reliability of financial information, while also emphasizing the significance of evaluation in financial management, involving the analysis of financial data to identify trends and support decision-making processes. Furthermore, the integration of automated information systems, as highlighted by Yandug et al. (2020), enhances the quality of work and decreases room for error in auditing and evaluation processes.

Table 8 presents the statistical analysis of the relationship between physical facilities development planning practices and financial resources management practices of public elementary schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. The Spearman's rho correlation coefficient between these two variables is 0.010. The p-value associated with this correlation coefficient is 0.885, indicating that the correlation is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) is not rejected. This suggests that there is no significant relationship between physical facilities development planning practices and financial resources management practices in the public elementary schools within the district.

In practical terms, findings imply that the level of financial resources management practices employed by these schools does not have a notable impact on their physical facilities development planning practices, and vice versa. Essentially, the way schools

manage their financial resources does not necessarily influence how they plan for the development of their physical facilities, and vice versa. This lack of significant correlation suggests that factors other than financial management practices might be influencing the planning and development of physical facilities in these schools. Therefore, policymakers and school administrators may need to explore additional factors or strategies to improve both physical facilities development planning and financial resources management practices in these public elementary schools in the Division of Quezon.

Unlike the findings of Villareal (2023), significant relationship was found between school heads' financial literacy practices and resources management for school development. Also, program for educational facilities is essentially a carefully thought-out collection of decisions for action that are focused on achieving certain objectives within predetermined time constraints. It will be a crucial component of the overall plan. Hence, the school's instructional program must be organized within the parameters of clearly defined educational goals. It will be cooperatively carried out by educators and the school administration.

Table 9 presents the problems encountered by school heads in both physical facilities and financial resources management in public elementary schools. In terms of physical facilities, the most significant challenges include insufficient funding for infrastructure development (4.43) interpreted as always encountered followed by shortage of classrooms (4.36), and deteriorating infrastructure / facilities (4.07). This can be traced back from lack of fundings due to small number of teachers and enrolment that is counted for MOOE for every month of the school year.

Similarly, in financial resources management, limited budgetary allocation (4.64) interpreted as always encountered was identified as the major problem. This is followed by complex budgeting processes (4.43) and budgeting and expenditure tracking practices that are consistently identified as significant problems interpreted as often encountered.

The findings indicate several significant implications for public elementary schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. Firstly, the prevalence of challenges such as insufficient funding for infrastructure development, deteriorating infrastructure, and a shortage of classrooms underscores the critical need for increased investment in physical facilities. Addressing these issues is crucial for creating safe, conducive learning environments that promote student well-being and academic success.

Secondly, the identified problems in financial resources management, including limited budgetary allocation, complex budgeting processes, and competing priorities, highlight the importance of more effective financial planning and management strategies. Schools must find ways to optimize their budget allocation processes, streamline financial reporting and accountability mechanisms, and enhance revenue generation and fundraising efforts to ensure adequate resources for educational programs and facilities maintenance.

Additionally, the lack of transparency and accountability in financial management practices underscores the necessity of implementing robust governance and oversight

mechanisms. Schools should prioritize transparency in financial decision-making processes, enhance accountability measures, and establish clear procedures for budgeting and expenditure tracking to build trust among stakeholders and ensure the efficient and equitable use of financial resources.

In general, these findings emphasize the importance of addressing both physical facilities and financial management challenges to enhance the quality of education and learning outcomes in public elementary schools. With the prioritization of investments in infrastructure development, improving financial planning and management practices, and enhancing transparency and accountability, schools can create an enabling environment that supports the holistic development of students and contributes to their academic success.

Similar with the current findings, numerous studies also revealed common challenges faced by school leaders in the management of financial resources, including issues with disbursement, utilization, and evaluation of funds, as highlighted by Mac Taner (2023). Similarly, Bantilan et al. (2023) identified various financial management challenges across different types of schools, ranging from inadequate staff assistance to delayed fund releases. However, common strategies such as prioritization, prompt liquidation, and shared governance were utilized by school leaders to address these challenges. Gaspar et al. (2022) further emphasized the importance of transparency and accountability in financial management, highlighting challenges such as late budget allocations and limited opportunities for training. These findings collectively underscore the critical need for school leaders to enhance their financial management skills, improve transparency, and engage stakeholders effectively to ensure optimal utilization of financial resources.

Table 10 presents the actions taken by the school heads to address specific problems in Physical Facilities and Financial Resources Management in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. In response to the major problems of insufficient funding for infrastructure development, the respondents requests for increased government funding and do resource allocation, redirection of underutilized school MOOE funds, and utilization of Special Education Fund (SEF) in coordination with local government units (LGUs) were prioritized.

For other identified problems that were often encountered such as outdated or deteriorating infrastructure, recalibration of available local funds through alignment and modification of school PPAs. Concerning the lack of expertise, the respondents held strengths and needs assessments (50.00) and attended different DepEd initiated online/virtual training and webinars. As to shortage of classroom, the respondents implement various construction programs such as building, repairing, and utilizing dilapidated structures (100).

As to limited access to amenities, the respondents intensified NGOs partnership with communities (71.43). In terms of community expectations and pressure, the respondents create opportunities for the community members to participate in the decision-making processes and project implementation (71.43). About problems in inspections of school

buildings and ground, the respondents addressed minor issues promptly to prevent them from escalating into major problems.

Lastly, concerning the students and teachers' distraction by facilities, the respondents schedule regular inspections with preventive maintenance (64.29) and inform the students and parents about the importance of maintaining a healthy learning environment (64.29).

Meanwhile, in terms of problems in financial resource management concerning the primary problem such as limited budgetary allocation, respondents developed a clear prioritization framework based on the needs assessment, focusing on critical areas that directly impact the students' learning and safety (71.43).

Moreover, all other problems were often encountered where in terms of complex budgeting processes, the respondents identified and eliminated unnecessary steps (57.14) and established clear communication channels (57.14). Also, in terms of financial reporting and accountability problems, the respondents implemented system where different individuals handle different aspect of financial management (71.43). About competing priorities and resource allocation challenges, the respondents create a transparent prioritization framework based on assessment needs (71.43). In terms of revenue generation and fundraising, the respondents conducted a thorough assessment of the school's needs and funding gaps, identifying areas where additional resources are crucial (78.57). Moreover, as to financial sustainability planning, the respondents forecast future income streams and expenses based on enrollment.

Additionally, as to problems in budgeting and expenditure tracking practices, the respondents established a standardized budgeting framework (64.29) and allocated resources based on identified needs and priorities. Lastly, concerning the lack of transparency and accountability in financial management, the respondents organized open meetings and forums (57.14) and provide training for school staff on financial transparency, accountability practices, and best practices in financial management (57.14).

Findings from the analysis showed several implications for public elementary schools. Firstly, prioritizing requests for increased government funding, resource allocation, and utilization of Special Education Fund (SEF) underscores the importance of adequate financial support for infrastructure development, ultimately enhancing the learning environment for students.

Similarly, recalibrating available local funds and engaging in partnerships with NGOs address the challenge of outdated infrastructure and limited access to amenities, emphasizing the importance of innovative solutions and community collaboration in addressing facility-related issues. Additionally, efforts to address community expectations and pressure by involving stakeholders in decision-making processes highlight the significance of transparent communication and community engagement in school management.

Furthermore, actions taken to improve financial resource management, such as developing prioritization frameworks, implementing standardized budgeting processes, and enhancing transparency and accountability, contribute to effective financial planning and utilization of resources, ultimately improving the overall financial health and sustainability of public elementary schools.

Similar to the findings in the current study, Mac Taner (2023) underscores the critical need to enhance school heads' knowledge and training in financial management practices, particularly in the disbursement and utilization of Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) funds, along with involving teachers and stakeholders in the budgetary process to ensure transparency. Meanwhile, Operario (2022) highlights a high level of perceived managerial competence among respondents and their consistent adherence to financial management protocols.

Part VI. Proposed Intervention Plan

The "**Upskilling School Heads on Managing Facilities and Financial Resources**" is an intervention program that is designed to empower the school heads, school administrators and administrative officers to take ownership of their school environment focusing on physical facilities such as prioritization, cost benefit analysis, capital planning as well as financial resources management concerning the budget preparations, resource mobilization, and auditing and evaluation.

By equipping the school heads and administrative officers with the necessary knowledge and tools, the program has the potential to create a more sustainable and supportive learning environment for the organization, students, teachers, stakeholders, and the community in general.

This intervention program designed to enable the school heads and administrative officers in Public Elementary schools within Third District of Quezon particularly Macalelon, Catanuan, Mulanay, General Luna and Pitogo in to effectively manage facilities and financial resources. The program aimed to address the challenges schools face in maintaining their physical facilities and infrastructure and optimizing financial resource allocation.

All the areas for improvement were identified based on the lowest mean scored indicators and the identified primary challenges in physical facilities and financial resource management. Hence, the proposed intervention plan is deemed research-based and data-driven to comprehensively address the identified bottlenecks for improvement as well as the major problems based on the responses and lens of the school heads.

Table 11 presents the overview of the proposed intervention plan with eight (8) areas for improvements with relevant eight (8) proposed actions. The proposed intervention plan is aimed at addressing areas for improvement in physical facilities development practices and financial resources management within the Third Congressional District of Quezon.

In terms of physical facilities development, the plan suggests prioritizing collaboration with stakeholders to assess and prioritize facility needs through regular meetings or forums, conducting cost-benefit analyses to ensure efficient allocation of resources, and creating a comprehensive capital plan based on identified issues.

For financial resources management, the plan recommends implementing standardized processes for budget preparation and data collection, strengthening partnerships with stakeholders to optimize resource mobilization, and instituting regular auditing and evaluation procedures to ensure financial accountability.

Specifically addressing the challenges of insufficient funding for infrastructure development and limited budgetary allocation, the plan suggests advocating for increased government funding, exploring alternative funding sources, and developing a comprehensive budget prioritization framework based on needs assessment.

These proposed actions aim to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of physical facilities development and financial management practices in public elementary schools within the district, ultimately enhancing the learning environment and resource utilization for students.

Same with the findings of Kuresoi et al., (2022), an intervention is crucial in improving aspects of the organization which may involves the individually planned and systematically monitored arrangement of procedures, adapted equipment and materials, accessible settings, and other interventions designed to help achieve a higher level of performance and success in school and community.

Conclusions

Summary

This research aimed to describe and analyze the relationship between Physical Facilities Development Planning Practices and Financial Resources Management Practices of Public Elementary Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. Specifically, it sought to answer the following the level of physical facilities development planning practices of public elementary schools in terms of Prioritization, Cost Benefits Analysis, and Capital Planning. Next is the level of financial resources management practices of schools in terms of Budget Preparation, Resource Mobilization, and Auditing and evaluation. Third, is the significant relationship between the physical facilities development planning practices and financial resources management practices of public elementary schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. The study was conducted using descriptive method of quantitative research with school heads and teachers as the respondents. Questionnaires were developed, validated, and piloted to gather the data that were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Lastly, the training program could be offered by the researcher based on the findings of the study to

capacitate the school heads in Physical Facilities Planning and Financial Resources Management. The study was conducted from January 2022 to December 2023.

Summary of Findings

Based on the data gathered the following findings were summarized:

1. On the Level of Physical Facilities Development Planning Practices of the School Heads

1.1 In terms of Prioritization was fully practiced which obtained a 4.26 general weighted mean which primarily concerns having system in place for regularly assessing the condition and needs of the school's physical facilities.

1.2 As to Cost benefit in the level of physical facilities development of school heads was highly practiced which obtained 3.96.mean which primarily involve having the knowledge and skills to conduct a thorough cost-benefit analysis and using the data and evidence to inform the cost-benefit analysis process.

1.3 With regards to the school heads' levels of physical facilities development planning practices, the capital planning was highly practiced with a 3.98 composite mean where respondents mostly enable the schools to meet the regulatory requirements for school physical facilities development.

2. On the Level of Physical Financial Resources Management Practices

2.1 The finding showed that the level of financial resources management practices of school Heads in terms of Budget Preparation was highly practiced which obtained 3.96 composite mean primarily dealing with identifying the time frame to determine the period for which you want to create the budget, such as a fiscal year, a calendar year, or a project timeline.

2.2 As to resource mobilization, the financial resources management practices of school heads was highly practiced which obtained 3.93 mean primarily dealing with presenting report in a timely manner in agreement with the format agreed to with the sponsor.

2.3 Concerning the auditing and evaluation, the school heads' financial resource management practices scored 3.80 and was highly practiced that mainly concern the provision of an independent assessment of the financial health and performance of an organization, and to identify any potential risks or areas for improvement.

3. On the relationship between Physical Facilities Development Planning Practices and Financial Resources management Practices.

The relationship between the physical facilities development was found to be not statistically significant ($p=.885$) at 0.05 level of significance. This finding suggests that

physical development planning is not associated with the resource management practices of public elementary schools.

4. On the problems encountered by the school head in Physical Facilities and Financial Resources Management:

In terms of physical facilities, the most significant challenges include insufficient funding for infrastructure development (4.43) that was always encountered followed by shortage of classrooms (4.36), and deteriorating infrastructure / facilities (4.07). Moreover, in terms of financial resources management, limited budgetary allocation (4.64) interpreted as always encountered was identified as the major problem along with complex budgeting processes (4.43) and budgeting and expenditure tracking practices that are consistently identified as significant problems interpreted as often encountered.

5. On the actions are taken by the school heads to address the problems encountered in Physical Facilities and Financial Resource Management:

For problems in physical facilities, the respondents such as insufficient funding for infrastructure development, respondents applied strategies such as advocating for increased government funding, reallocation of underutilized funds, and coordination with local government units for utilizing Special Education Funds. Similarly, in financial resource management, actions such as developing clear prioritization frameworks, eliminating unnecessary budgeting steps, and implementing systems for financial reporting and accountability were prioritized. Moreover, proactive measures such as engaging stakeholders in decision-making processes, intensifying partnerships with NGOs, and conducting regular inspections to prevent issues escalation were adopted to ensure efficient resource allocation and infrastructure maintenance.

6. An intervention plan titled “**Upskilling School Heads on Managing Facilities and Financial Resources**” for school heads and administrative officers is designed based on the research results to update and reequip the concerned personnel in optimizing the schools’ Physical Facilities Planning and Financial Resources Management.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following were recommended:

1. Given the generally high level of physical facilities development planning practices, it is suggested that the DepEd officials to continue fostering a culture of collaboration and stakeholder engagement in prioritizing physical facility needs considering the identified problem. Regular meetings or forums involving stakeholders are also recommended to be established to assess and prioritize these needs based on importance and urgency. Also, a policy that will strengthen the practices for physical facility management is suggested focusing on collaboration.

2. With the highly practiced level of financial resources management, school heads and administrative officers should focus on implementing standardized processes for budget preparation, resource mobilization, and auditing and evaluation. Strengthening partnerships with stakeholders, streamlining communication channels, and enhancing financial management practices will optimize resource mobilization efforts and ensure accountability. Likewise, a policy for school implementation is suggested to be emphasized concerning financial matter documents, transparency, and accountability.
 3. Since no significant relationship was found between physical facilities development planning practices and financial resources management practices, school heads and administrative officers should emphasize the importance of integrating these two aspects for comprehensive school management. Collaborative efforts should be made to bridge any existing gaps and ensure alignment between physical facilities planning and financial resource allocation.
 4. In light of the major challenges encountered, particularly insufficient funding for infrastructure development and limited budgetary allocation, school heads, parents, and learners are suggested to advocate for increased government funding and explore alternative funding sources with the help of the LGU and NGOs with their special education funds and supports. Active involvement in decision-making processes and raising awareness about these challenges will empower stakeholders to contribute to finding viable solutions with community initiatives for the benefits of the school.
 5. To address the identified problems, such as insufficient funding and limited budgetary allocation, collaborative efforts between DepEd officials, school heads, parents, and learners is suggested. Developing a prioritization framework based on actual and immediate school needs, alongside exploring cost-saving measures and alternative funding sources, will optimize budget allocation and infrastructure development. The DepEd officials are also suggested to design policy focusing on review of the contextual needs of the school beyond mere enrolment data for budget allocation and sourcing that can be proposed for the local board or LGU.
 6. To support the intervention plan titled “Upskilling School Heads on Managing Facilities and Financial Resources,” school heads and administrative officers are recommended for collaborative review with the parents and learners on the intervention for school implementation. They are also suggested to participate in training programs aimed at enhancing their skills in physical facilities planning and financial resource management. This initiative will ensure that they are adequately equipped to address the challenges and effectively manage school resources.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

In the conduct of this study, the researcher firstly secured informed consent that was obtained from all participants, including school administrators, teachers, and other relevant stakeholders, prior to their involvement in the study. Participants were provided with clear information about the purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits of the research, and they were given the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence. Confidentiality and anonymity were also maintained to protect the privacy

of participants, ensuring that their responses and personal information were kept secure and not disclosed without their explicit consent. Additionally, the research conducted with integrity, honesty, and transparency, avoiding any form of deception or manipulation. The researchers adhered to ethical guidelines and standards set forth by relevant institutions and regulatory bodies such as the university and DepEd, such as obtaining approval from ethics committees or review boards. Lastly, the findings of the study should be reported accurately and objectively, without bias or distortion, to contribute meaningfully to the body of knowledge and promote the welfare of the participants and the broader community without harm ensuring that the respondents will be safe and secured all throughout the study.

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